

Assessing Writing Skills Through Viewing-Based Writing Prompts Among Senior High School Students

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Abstract: This study aimed to investigate the challenges that Grade 12 senior high school students encountered in writing output through viewing-based prompts. The researchers examined students' writing output to better understand their writing abilities and identify areas for improvement. This study aimed to assess writing challenges in cohesion, coherence, clarity of ideas, writing mechanics, and organization and structure, and to propose an intervention program to address the challenges participants faced in writing. The participants are the entire Grade 12 student population of Laboratory High School in NUEST. The study used qualitative-descriptive research and document analysis to assess participants' writing output. The instruments of the study were a viewing-based prompt and a rubric. The results of the study: in coherence and clarity of ideas, the participants' interpretations show creativity and logical flow; in cohesion, the participants used transitional devices ineffectively; and in writing mechanics and structure, a large portion of the participants. The researchers proposed an intervention titled "Mechanics Drills and Idea Sequencing for Effective Writing" to enhance students' grammar and writing structure skills.

Keywords: *Challenges in Writing, Viewing-Based Writing, Viewing Skills, Writing Skills.*

Introduction

Effective writing involves correct grammar, spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and vocabulary, and allows students to communicate ideas or thoughts clearly and concisely. (Sakkir, 2018). Students need to follow a structured process to write effectively. First, students should organize their ideas. Next, you must check and review the output for errors. To ensure the ideas are well-connected and understandable. Last, revising is also an important part of the process; it helps improve the clarity of ideas and rewrite the output. Additionally, students need to find ways to improve their use of the language, using it more concisely. The writing process is not just about putting words on paper but about improving the text through multiple stages. Following these steps, students can produce well-organized, clear, and effective writing (Yilmaz & Erkol, 2015).

Viewing-based writing prompts involve watching a video or visual content and writing about it, and provide an approach to assess and improve students' writing abilities. A visual prompt can be used as the main material for writing output. According to a study, using pictures helps students generate creative ideas, engage more in the activity, and stay focused on learning (Apsari, 2017). A visual prompt is useful because it encourages participation and attention. Text prompts offer clear writing instructions through visual prompts. These prompts help students understand the topic better and create more meaningful content (Suharmi, 2015). Both visual and text prompts can enhance students' creativity and critical thinking in writing tasks. It serves as a useful tool to improve students' writing skills through the writing process. By using these prompts, students can produce creative and well-organized writing outputs. Prompts, whether visual or written, have an important role in supporting the writing process.

By analyzing students' outputs to these prompts, researchers can identify areas where students may struggle, such as interpretation, sentence structure, and organization. This method develops students' critical thinking, coherent thought organization, and effective expression. According to Somanathan (2024), writing prompts can generate creative ideas and help develop good writing habits. By regularly using prompts, students can improve their communication skills and analytical thinking abilities.

This study aimed to investigate the challenges that Grade 12 senior high school students encounter when writing using viewing-based writing prompts. By examining students' responses to these prompts, researchers can better understand the writing abilities and identify areas for improvement in students' outputs. Overcoming writing challenges requires targeted interventions that improve students' writing output. By applying specific strategies, learners can develop stronger claims and more effective writing skills, thereby improving the quality and readability of their work.

This study aimed to assess the writing skills of senior high school students through viewing-based writing prompts. Specifically, it sought to describe the participants' demographic profile by sex, grade level, and strand. It also aimed to determine the challenges in the writing output of Grade 12 students in terms of cohesion, coherence, clarity of ideas, writing mechanics, and organization and structure. Furthermore, the study aimed to propose an intervention program based on the challenges participants encountered in writing.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

This chapter presents a comprehensive overview of relevant research, including completed theses, generalizations, methodologies, and other key findings. This information serves as a foundation for understanding the current study and its context. Thematic analysis, a method for analyzing qualitative data, is relevant to studying the impact of viewing prompts on writing output. Thematic analysis involves identifying themes within data through written output by viewing prompts. By applying thematic analysis to written outputs through viewing prompts, researchers can identify common themes, patterns, and ideas brought by the prompt. This approach offers important insights into how visual influence in creative interpretation and writing (Caulfield, 2023).

Writing Skills

Writing is an essential skill for communication, creativity, and personal insights. According to Sharma (2020), writing supports can help to have self-awareness and social growth. It shows that people express thoughts or ideas on different topics through writing. This aligns with Olson's (2024) study, which argued that understanding a writing system is vital for engaging with society and fulfilling various social functions. Writing also fosters personal growth by encouraging students to explore themselves in creative ways. Also, Pineda (2023) said that creative writing in Filipino involves mastering essential storytelling and expressing thoughts to make the writing more engaging. To enhance writing skills, writers should focus on developing the sequence of the story or ideas about a certain topic. It can help the readers to understand the context and find it interesting. Writing is another way to communicate ideas, opinions, or thoughts to others. In writing, it must follow the writing process to make the output effective in conveying the message.

Viewing Skills

In the modern era, viewing skills are crucial to understanding and interpreting the visual aids. Visual materials were used to engage the students in the topic. According to Donaghy (2023), the 3Cs (color, camera, and character) and 3Ss (story, setting, and sound) provide structured approaches for analyzing visual material and helping students develop critical thinking skills. This method focuses on elements like color, camera angles, story, and setting to identify the messages of visual materials. Incorporating visual literacy into education prepares students to move through a world of visuals and writing, where images and texts can work together to convey meaning. This skill is particularly important in today's digital age, where students encounter abundant visual content. The studies utilize viewing skills in the classroom to enhance students' interpretation of visual materials. Viewing skills involve watching and interpreting visual content, which can enhance other areas of learning. For example, Candelaria (2023) looks at how educators perceive these skills, while Carolino & Queroda (2019) examine how viewing skills are integrated with teaching strategies and materials. Dalagan (2019) shows that viewing can serve as a foundation to develop other skills, such as 21st-century literacy. Pujadas & Muñoz (2019) highlight how extensive viewing can help improve language learning. Assessing writing skills through viewing-based writing prompts, these findings are relevant because they suggest that viewing can enhance critical thinking skills, such as writing output. Through visual prompts, students can develop a better understanding and creativity in writing, aligning with the idea that viewing skills help improve other learning skills. The viewing skill may help students to have a deeper understanding of the images. When students can clearly visualize and understand what is being explained, they can use critical thinking to develop in-depth interpretations and insights.

Viewing-Based Writing Prompt

Visual prompts are highlighted as tools that enhance students' creativity and critical thinking. According to Main (2022) and Teacherinspo123 (2024), emphasizing how visuals help students connect the sequence of writing tasks encourages imagination and critical thinking. These prompts can boost descriptive writing, storytelling, and vocabulary development in students. Using a variety of visual materials engages students and supports the development of their writing. A visual-based prompt makes the writing process more engaging and expressive to encourage students to formulate ideas. Writing prompts, whether in the form of questions, statements, or pictures, must provide a structured approach to guide students' thinking, helping them state ideas clearly (Beecher & Firestone, 2023). Also, Avitia (2021) said that writing prompts can help and guide students to be creative writers by providing specific topics or contexts. These prompts can be based on personal experiences, observations, and insights to encourage writers to explore new ideas. Visual writing prompts, in particular, stimulate creativity by asking writers to describe images to evoke detailed narratives. By using such prompts, writers can practice developing imagination, improve descriptive skills, and create engaging stories.

The Role of Rubrics

The theme of rubrics as a tool for fair and consistent grading is explored by several writers. According to Haugnes & Russell (2018), research shows that rubrics help students, especially those from underrepresented groups (Jonsson, 2014; Winkelmes, 2016). Rubrics clarify expectations, reducing confusion and ensuring that all students, regardless of background, are graded fairly. Calkins and Winkelmes (2018) argue that rubrics strengthen students' sense of belonging and lead to better academic outcomes. Students may struggle to meet expectations without rubrics; it hinders performance and the fairness of writing output (Shapiro et al., 2023). Therefore, rubrics are an important tool in the writing process, fostering clear communication about assessment criteria and promoting fair grading practices.

The rubric helps evaluate students' outputs by specific criteria, such as cohesion, coherence, clarity of ideas, writing mechanics, and organization and structure. Cohesion refers to using devices like repetition, conjunctions, and referencing to link together the ideas. It helps the text flow smoothly. According to Knight (2024). Cohesion in writing is crucial for the unity of ideas and for easily understanding the text. Cohesion involves transitional devices to create a focused and clear text. Also focuses on the connection between sentences within a paragraph, ensuring a logical flow of ideas. While coherence is about the overall logic and clarity of the text, it ensures that the ideas are consistent and understandable. Research. Life (2024) explains that coherence in academic writing is crucial for clarity and credibility. A coherent paper presents ideas smoothly, allowing readers to easily follow the ideas and understand the context. The text used cohesive devices correctly to make the overall message clear and understandable for the readers (Kaur, 2018). The clarity of ideas rubric checks whether the main points are clear, focused, and well-explained. Clear writing means both clear ideas and clear language. A clear idea has a clear purpose, shown in every sentence and paragraph, with supporting quotes explained and linked to the main points. (Agnes Scott College, 2023). While writing mechanics, it is about grammar, vocabulary, and how well language is used. According to Firestone & Mateski (2023), correct writing mechanics, spelling, punctuation, and capitalization are essential for clarity and effective communication. These technical aspects consider the impact of a text's readability and flow, ensuring the author's intended meaning is conveyed and the ideas are vivid. The organization and structure criterion evaluates how well the writing output is organized through transitions between ideas. Naval Postgraduate School (2025) explains that a well-structured paper demonstrates a strong introduction and conclusion, a clear thesis statement, and effective topic sentences. This helps students understand how to address weaknesses in their writing and allows instructors to provide targeted feedback (Maverick Learning and Educational Applied Research Nexus, 2021). The rubric may give a fair judgment of the writing output.

Intervention Program for the Challenges in Writing

To address the challenges students face in writing, we must implement an intervention program to enhance and develop their skills. It consistently shows that explicit grammar instruction significantly improves students' writing and produces meaningful writing activities. According to the British Council. (2015), the 'Sing it' through music enhances memory, making it a powerful tool for learning grammar. Songs provide a repetitive, rhythmic structure that helps students engage in incorporating grammar rules and vocabulary. The British Council highlights that songs can reinforce grammar naturally and motivate learners. Allowing students to sing requires proper pronunciation and fluency. Also, from the intervention "Say it," Saddler (2017) explains that oral practice is essential for helping students apply grammar rules they have learned. Students speak for 2 minutes during speaking activities that practice grammar rules. Teaching grammar through sentences helps students understand how grammar works in real writing, especially when revising. Games like building sentences with word cards make learning fun and help students use grammar correctly. This helps students improve their grammar and write better.

It is essential to completely use the three parts of the essay to state clearly the ideas about the context. According to Moxie (2023), use all three parts of your essay to clearly explain the ideas. Use a "Meal Plan" (Main Idea, Evidence, Analysis, Link) to organize the essay. Many students struggle with essay organization, which makes their writing unclear. The Meal Plan helps students by guiding them to state a main point, provide evidence, explain it, and connect it to other ideas. This improves essay structure. Other methods like PIE (point, illustration, explanation) also help. Practice and teacher feedback are important for these methods to work well. Structured writing plans like the Meal Plan are effective ways to improve essay organization. These interventions were effective in addressing students' challenges in grammar and writing structure.

Writing serves as a powerful means of communication and self-expression, while visual prompt strategies encourage creativity and critical thinking. Rubrics provide essential, fair grading and consistent expectations for students. These themes highlight the importance of structured approaches to both writing and visual skills in education, contributing to the development of the organization of ideas, correct usage of grammatical rules, and creative thinking. An intervention program helps students overcome and improve their weaknesses in writing essays.

Writing skills are fundamental for effective communication, creativity, and personal growth, enabling individuals to express thoughts clearly to others (Sharma, 2020; Olson, 2024; and Pineda, 2023). Writing proficiency improves when students focus on organizing ideas logically and following a structured writing process. Writing and viewing skills are essential in the digital age for interpreting visual materials and fostering critical thinking, with frameworks like the 3Cs and 3Ss helping students analyze visual content (Donaghy, 2023). While viewing-based writing prompts enhance creativity through descriptive and narrative skills by encouraging students to connect visuals with writing (Main, 2022; Teacherinspo123, 2024; Beecher & Firestone, 2023; Avitia, 2021). Rubrics play an important role in fair and consistent assessment by clarifying criteria such as cohesion, coherence, clarity, mechanics, and organization, which guide students in improving their writing and help teachers provide targeted feedback (Haugnes & Russell, 2018; Knight, 2024; Research. Life, 2024; Firestone & Mateski, 2023; Naval Postgraduate School, 2025). To address challenges in writing, intervention programs incorporating explicit grammar instruction, oral practice, and engaging activities like music and sentence-building games have proven effective in enhancing students' grammar and writing structure (British Council, 2015; Saddler, 2017; Moxie, 2023). These studies highlight the importance of incorporating writing and viewing skills, using structured assessment tools, and applying targeted interventions to develop students' writing communication, creativity, and critical thinking abilities.

Methodology

Research Design

Qualitative research helps us understand deeper aspects of real-world problems by exploring people's experiences, thoughts, and behaviors rather than just focusing on numbers. In the study of writing skills, it can be used to understand how students think and feel about writing tasks, like those based on viewing prompts (Tenny & Brannan, 2022). In this study, document analysis is a vital qualitative research technique that systematically examines electronic and physical documents to interpret meanings and extract relevant information. By integrating document analysis within a qualitative framework, the study gains comprehensive insights into students' writing abilities, providing a nuanced understanding of the interaction between viewing-based prompts and writing skill acquisition (Indeed Editorial Team, 2025). In this context, the research uses a qualitative descriptive design to provide a detailed understanding of the students' writing abilities in response to viewing-based prompts. Qualitative research methods are employed to gather details on students' writing skills using prompts. This approach emphasizes exploring how students interpret and respond to the prompts, offering a deeper insight into the processes involved in writing development. The findings from this qualitative research are expected to offer valuable insights into how viewing-based writing prompts can influence and enhance writing skills among senior high school students (Sirisilla, 2023). The researcher used visual prompts to assess the writing skills of Grade 12 students through viewing-based prompts, and the rubrics will serve as the instrument for judging the writing output.

Research Locale

The study will be conducted at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (Gabaldon Campus) (NEUST), located at Barangay North, Poblacion, Gabaldon, Nueva Ecija. The NUEST is the only state university in the town; it is surrounded by various establishments. The senior high school students of Laboratory High School at the NEUST Gabaldon Campus will be the study's participants.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study used purposive sampling. A sampling technique where the researchers choose to examine populations with particular characteristics (McCombes, 2019). The senior high school students at the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology during AY 2024-2025 are selected as participants.

Table 1.

Table of Participants

Grade Level	Male	Female	Total
Grade 12 GAS	23	12	35
Grade 12 AFA	4	11	15
Total			50

The target participants for this study are the Senior High School students at the Laboratory High School of NEUST, Gabaldon Campus. The Grade 12 GAS (General Academic Strand) is composed of twelve (12) males and twenty-three (23) females with a total of thirty-five (35) students. Lastly, the Grade 12 AFA comprises four (4) males and eleven (11) females, for a total of fifteen (15). The total number of students in the study is 50 Grade 12 Senior High Students.

Research Instruments

Researchers highlight the effectiveness of rubrics in assessing essays. Rubrics provide clear grading criteria, improving efficiency and clarifying expectations for students (Utah Education Network, 2023). It may help to define the quality of students' work and the quality of feedback. This study uses picture prompts as a viewing-based writing assessment tool for senior high school students. The prompts provide a visual stimulus to initiate writing, minimizing the blank-page anxiety often experienced by students. By analyzing student responses to these prompts, the study assesses writing skills, specifically focusing on descriptive language and sentence structure. The visual nature of the prompts encourages detailed descriptions and creative narratives. The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of picture prompts in identifying students' strengths and weaknesses in written communication (Mitchell, 2023).

Analytic rubrics, a specific type, use a grid format to offer detailed feedback across multiple criteria (Mateski & Carnevale, 2023). The rubric criteria are cohesion, coherence, clarity of ideas, writing mechanics, and organization & structure, while the levels and scoring scale are excellent (4), good (3), fair (2), and needs improvement (1). This approach allows for more specific and fair grading, benefiting both students and instructors by providing clarity and reducing grading time for complex assignments. In studies assessing writing skills through viewing-based prompts, rubrics provide a structured, transparent evaluation framework.

Procedure of the Study

The study will use picture prompts and rubrics as the main instruments of the data collection. After the approval of the research letter of permission forwarded to the Office of the Principal for issuance of the research permits. A copy of the letter was delivered to the teacher and the study participants, explaining the nature and purpose of the study. The writing outputs are checked by three (3) raters, including a researcher and an advisor, and, lastly, the data interpretation.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical considerations are essential guidelines for conducting research, particularly when involving human participants. Researchers must adhere to a strict code of conduct to ensure the rights of those involved. The primary goals of human research often include understanding real-life phenomena, investigating effective treatments, studying behaviors, and improving lives. The choices made regarding research topics and methodologies must align with ethical principles. These considerations play an important role in protecting participants' rights, enhancing the validity of research findings, and maintaining academic integrity. While this article primarily focuses on ethical considerations in human research, it is important to acknowledge that ethical principles (Bhandari, 2024). The researcher ensured ethical conduct throughout the study. Participants are informed that their participation is voluntary, and the purpose of the study is explained before they complete the questionnaire. Consent obtained, ensuring transparency and honesty. The researchers also prioritized participants' confidentiality and identity. Finally, to avoid plagiarism and fraud, all sources used in the study will be properly acknowledged.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the study's findings according to the rubrics developed by the researchers and validated by the English language teachers. To gather data, the researchers reported that Grade 12 AFA comprises four (4) males and eleven (11) females, and Grade 12 GAS comprises twelve (12) males and twenty-three (23) females, with a picture depicting two people earning money in different ways.

"On the left side, a person without disability finds a convenient job through pleasing and asking others for help. But beyond these actions, he had his own stories and struggles, and ended up begging for sympathy. On the right side, a person with a disability carries heavy baggage and chooses to work to earn money by his sweat. His dedication became his strength, and his weakness is his motivation to continue to strike harder in life. These people have their own stories and struggles, but still fight and do their best to live."

The students were tasked with writing a 200-word essay based on their interpretations of the visual prompts, encouraging diverse perspectives and responses. The purpose of this study is to assess the writing skills of grade 12

students through view-based prompts. To ensure objectivity, a rubric encompassing key writing aspects was used. This rubric included the criteria of coherence, cohesion, clarity of ideas, writing mechanics, and organization and structure.

Thematic Analysis

This data analysis section describes a qualitative study that analyzes writing prompts through a view-based approach. Data collection began with the assessment of Grade 12 students' papers. The researchers used open coding to identify five emergent themes: (1) Cohesion, (2) Coherence, (3) Clarity of Ideas, (4) Writing Mechanics, and (5) Organization & Structure. The data showed that students' work with the writing prompts often fell into five main categories. The following pages present these experiences using the students' works. This helps readers better understand the students' thoughts and in-depth interpretation of the viewing-based prompt.

Interpretation and creativity

Table 2 presents participants' performance in interpretation and creativity. Creativity and interpretation are needed to shape how to understand and express ideas. Creativity allows individuals to generate thoughts and concepts, while interpretation involves making sense of information, experiences, or works of art through personal insight and analysis. These two possessed the writing skills to express their ideas. In this writing, the outputs of Grade 12 students revealed creativity and in-depth interpretation in their discussion of the given viewing-based prompt.

Table 2.

Interpretation and Creativity.

Performance Level	Rating	Participants	Description
Excellent	4	3	Ideas are clear and well-written, with supporting details, good insight, and deep analysis and interpretation of the picture.
Good	3	18	Good analysis, clear interpretations, and well-organized ideas, but have minor lapses; ambiguity, lack of transitions, insufficient explanation, personal insights, and need more depth and supporting details
Fair	2	16	Some ideas and interpretations presented lacked depth, explanation, personal insights, and supporting details, and were often unclear or ambiguous, with disorganization.
Need Improvement	1	13	Only describes what is in the picture; lacks in-depth analysis, creativity, and clarity; and presents ideas that are ambiguous, redundant, and underdeveloped. Had no insights or a clear topic about the picture.

In terms of participants' interpretation and creativity, a few received excellent marks for demonstrating deep, insightful, and well-supported analysis. Participants critically interpreted the visual prompt, and it expressed the hidden meaning.

"Harsh reality of economic imbalance."

"Society, wealth, and opportunities are unfairly distributed."

Participants explain that the visual prompts are about inequality and economic imbalance. The harsh reality of society people with or without disabilities cannot receive equal opportunities. The creativity shown and the deep analysis of the visual prompt.

In the good rating, the majority of participants had a clear understanding and organized ideas, but needed to enhance depth, clarity, and personal insight.

"Perseverance in one's own sweat, and one relies on others' generosity."

"Two different situations of having disabilities, but they have their own ways to earn money."

"It's about how people deal with poverty and challenges."

"Both victims of poverty and social issues."

"Having ability to find solution"

"Only minds limits person capabilities."

Participants interpreted it that poverty is one of the problems of unfair treatment, and the capabilities of a person cannot be used by the manipulation of the mind. The ideas are clearly stated but need stronger support to make strong claims. Most participants received a Fair rating, struggled with depth and clarity, and often provided limited or vague interpretations. The participants cannot explain the ideas clearly, leading to insufficient supporting details.

"Everyone faces different kinds of challenges and hardships."

"Unfair treatment of society"

"Having a struggle has a purpose"

"Different situation, and realities of labor."

The participants' ideas are about hardships beyond challenges, struggles with purpose, and different types of labor. These ideas cannot be further explained due to issues that have caused ambiguity and a lack of clarity. In this rating, Needs Improvement, participants' interpretations have no depth or creativity.

*"Person with a disability work to earn money, but person without disability
asked others for money."*

"Had no specific ideas."

The ideas are undeveloped and lack specificity. The participants only describe the viewing prompt, what is in the picture, and cannot critically analyze it. In creativity, most of the participants deeply interpreted the visual prompt with supporting details and clearly explained the claims. But some of the students had a tough time expressing their ideas and claims about the visual prompt. According to Crossley, Roscoe, and McNamara (2016), clarity, achieved through precise and accessible language, can create an effective essay. Defining key terms early and avoiding assumptions about the reader's knowledge prevent confusion. Concise writing is encouraged by evaluating sentence length and avoiding overly complex structures, which can convey vague meaning. The study stresses avoiding jargon and unnecessary wording, as the strength of an essay is in how it presents its ideas.

Grammar

Grammar is the system of rules and structures that govern how words, phrases, and sentences are formed in a language, ensuring clarity and coherence in communication. It helps writers and speakers convey ideas precisely and effectively, making the messages easier to understand and more credible. Mastering grammar allows for accurate expression. This section evaluates the use of cohesive devices in the writing outputs of Grade 12 students. The use of transition devices that link ideas and paragraphs allows for a smooth flow of information.

Table 3.

Participants' Grammar Rating.

Performance Level	Rating	Participants	Description
Excellent	4	1	Highly effective use of cohesive devices, enabling a clear and smooth flow of ideas throughout the text.
Good	3	16	Effective use of cohesive devices, strong use and appropriately used transitions, but have minor lapses, including limited range, slight redundancy, and minor issues.
Fair	2	26	Inconsistent or limited, redundant transitions, missing punctuation, and improper use of cohesive devices result in unclear or poorly connected ideas.
Need Improvement	1	7	Significantly struggled with cohesion; inappropriate use, no transition devices, and lacked proper transition devices, resulting in unclear or disjointed writing.

In terms of using transitional devices, only one participant achieved an excellent rating, demonstrating mastery in using cohesive devices. This participant employed the transitional devices correctly and stated ideas clearly. Most participants demonstrated a good rating in cohesion, though with minor issues due to redundant or improper use of transitional devices. A few participants showed fair cohesion, with inconsistent or unclear connections. Some of the participants struggled into the Needs Improvement category, indicating a lack of basic cohesion skills. The results highlighted that participants who struggled used transitional devices that needed to be enhanced for clarity and flow in their writing. In mechanics, Grade 12 participants' essays were evaluated based on grammar, punctuation, spelling, and overall writing accuracy.

Table 4.*Cohesion Skills.*

Performance Level	Rating	Participants	Description
Excellent	4	None	None
Good	3	1	Minimal errors in grammar and punctuation, and unnecessary words.
Fair	2	18	Grammatical errors such as improper punctuation, a few spelling mistakes, unnecessary words, improper use of verbs, run-on sentences, Subject-Verb Agreement, redundancy, missing words, and incorrect use of symbols.
Need Improvement	1	31	Numerous issues: incorrect verb usage, missing words, unnecessary words, run-on sentences, capitalization issues, subject-verb agreement issues, excessive use of unnecessary words, excessive conjunctions, missing commas, misplaced words and phrases, improper transition devices, misspelled words, and incorrect symbols.

Only one participant, 29, demonstrated a Good rating in writing mechanics with minimal errors. While in the Fair rating, some participants are showing moderate proficiency but need improvement in grammar and punctuation. In subject-verb-agreement error, "*The picture is represent (representing two kind (kinds of people". The be-verb "is" is not necessary, and since the subject is singular, the verb must be in S-form. "*The image show (shows us.", and, "*The one person have (has a complete body set", no need to use the article "the" and since the subject is singular, the verb should be "has" not "have". "*The image show a (shows the) same kind of disability", the wrong usage of the article, instead of an article "a" it should be an article "the" and since the subject is singular (image), the verb must be in S-form (shows). "*I remember when Sir Louie said(,) his perspective on beggars". the lack of punctuation after the word "said". "They (he) have (has) the strength and ability to find a job but they (he) rely on others kindness", in describing the beggar, participant 1 use third plural pronoun "they" instead of third singular pronoun "he". Lack of comma; "*I think its (it's) a matter of making your own choices", the correct "it's" means "it" + "is", not a possessive "its". In capitalization error; "*As i (1) analyze the image...", the letter "I" should always capitalize. Error on spelling and spacing; "*To build a fairer (fair) society, we must knowledgethese (acknowledge these issues". The wrong spelling of "fair", and "acknowledge", and spacing of the words "knowledgethese". These affect in the clarity of the ideas and flow of ideas. And most of the participants received Needs Improvement numerous errors that greatly affect clarity and readability.********

In subject-verb-agreement error; "*It challenge (challenges) viewers to reflect on their own attitudes (attitudes) toward work and adversity" it should be "challenges" since the subject is singular. "attitudes" is the correct spelling. Wrong tenses of verb and missing Be-verb; "*The picture describing (describes) the people who (are) both fighting in life". It lacks of B-verb "are". The paper of contains redundancy of words and written in all Caps lock. "*IN MY OWN UNDERSTANDING" no need to use the word "own". Instead of describing, it is better to say (describes). Subject-verb-agreement error. The be-verb "is" is not necessary, and since the subject is singular, the verb must be in S-form. "*The beggar have (has) hands and feet". Lack of punctuation, wrong use of preposition, wrong usage of pronoun, and subject-verb-agreement error "*In life people faces (face) different challenges" lack of comma after the words "In life" and since the subject (people) is plural, the verb is in base form (face). Lack of comma and subject-verb-agreement error "*To me the picture represent (represents)..", "*To me the beggar represent (represents)..." It should be used as a singular verb because the beggar and picture are singular. "*The image shows that anybody has a freedom of choices (choice)." The word "choices" should be a singular verb because the subject is singular. Participant 15 "*WHEN I LOOKED AT THE PHOTO..." Should be written in lower case. Capitalization error "*even i don't (if I do not) have that others have i (I) don't need to be shy just i (I) need is (to) accept what i (I) have". The letter "I" should always capitalize, and in arrangement of word. It should be "I just" instead of "just i". Error on arrangement of word "*You always a have choice" the word "have" should come first before the letter "a". "the both people(the both of them) have different struggler (struggles) in life". The usage of the words "both people" instead of "both***********

of them" in referring to the beggar and the person with disability. And it is not "struggler", but "struggles". These numerous errors cannot effectively convey the ideas. The results highlighted that grammatical errors can make the writing output vague and unclear.

In grammar, it is crucial to use it correctly to convey the ideas. The study by Bulqiyah, Mahbub, and Nugraheni (2021) directly aligns with your findings on affective and cognitive problems in essay writing, with the importance of cohesion for achieving high essay ratings. The challenges, often influenced by teaching strategies, significantly impact cohesion in producing well-rated essays. Therefore, applying effective writing strategies and focusing on cohesion can help students improve their writing output. Also, it reveals that incorrect grammar, punctuation, and spelling errors significantly hinder clarity and coherence in student writing, often requiring targeted interventions. It emphasizes that correct usage is important for clarity and well-served ideas. The study's recommendation to strengthen cognitive strategies and provide repeated, self-regulated practice aligns with research advocating scaffolded instruction and corrective feedback to improve mechanical accuracy (Lopez, 2023). Grammar is the foundation of writing, helping explain ideas clearly and avoid vagueness.

Structure and Organization of Ideas

Organization of ideas and structure is crucial for creating a clear and effective concept. A well-structured writing output begins with a general statement to engage the reader, followed by background information that narrows the focus, and ends with a clear thesis statement that outlines the main argument or purpose of the essay. Organizing ideas logically in this way helps set the tone and direction for the entire piece, making it easier for readers to follow and understand the message. In this section, we present the results of the essays, the connectedness of each idea, and the logical order. The study revealed how Grade 12 students' written outputs progressed with ideas and logical organization about the viewing-based.

Table 5.

Structure and Organization of Ideas.

Performance Level	Rating	Participants	Description
Excellent	4	3	Demonstrate a clear and logical progression of ideas, with logically organized, well-connected thoughts, and in-depth explanations supported by relevant details.
Good	3	18	Show some progression of ideas, but minor lapses include a lack of sufficient justification or personal reflection, unclear structure, improper spacing, and a lack of a strong conclusion.
Fair	2	16	Suffer from disconnected, disorganized, or poorly spaced content; a lack of supporting details; and disjointed paragraphs, and issues of word choice hinder the clarity and persuasiveness of the writing.
Need Improvement	1	13	Major lapses include a lack of progression in the idea, a disorganized structure, and underdeveloped ideas.

In the flow of ideas, only one participant achieved excellent cohesion, demonstrating mastery in linking ideas smoothly. Most participants received Good, showing mostly effective cohesion with minor errors, a lack of justification, and insufficient insight to support strong claims. In Fair Rating, a few participants exhibit inconsistent or limited cohesion, resulting in unclear ideas. Several students rated Needs Improvement and struggled significantly with cohesion, resulting in confusing, disjointed writing. The results highlighted the need to focus on the consistency of the flow of ideas. In the writing structure, the output must follow a logical progression from the participants' essays. The study revealed how Grade 12 students structured writing and the flow of ideas about the viewing-based.

Table 6.

Linking Ideas.

Performance Level	Rating	Participants	Description
Excellent	4	3	Well-organized with a clear introduction, well-developed body paragraphs supported by insightful arguments and supporting details, and a concise conclusion that effectively presents the main ideas.
Good	3	15	Have minor lapses, including those needed for more in-depth interpretation, structural lapses, and a lack of sufficient evidence to support the claims.
Fair	2	14	Undeveloped parts of essays caused a lack of sufficient supporting details, poor organization, and a lack of paragraph separation, affecting the progression of the paper's organization and structure
Need Improvement	1	18	Numerous issues and errors include three parts of the essay combined in a single paragraph, a lack of supporting details and strong arguments, missing parts of the essays, and a lack of organization, which caused ambiguity.

In structure, a few participants got Excellent and demonstrated strong essay structure with clear, well-developed parts and insightful arguments. While several participants got a good basic essay structure, there were minor lapses and a need for deeper analysis and better transitions between the sentences. And many participants had fair, underdeveloped structures, missing conclusions, poor organization, and weak supporting details, which led to structural errors. In the Needs Improvement rating, the majority of students struggled with fundamental essay organization, often combining parts into a single paragraph, lacking clarity, and omitting essential elements. In the study, most participants did not follow the essay's three parts and had numerous structural errors.

The organization and structure must be well-organized to ensure a clear flow of ideas. According to Crossley, Roscoe, and McNamara (2016), essays with clear, well-organized arguments and a concise thesis receive higher coherence ratings and overall quality scores. It is important to monitor the flow of ideas to avoid some minor issues that affect the writing output. Maintaining a consistent flow of argument structure enhances the quality of writing. Also, by developing a writing plan that includes outlining main points and managing timelines, students can create clearer, more coherent essay structures, thereby reducing disorganization and enhancing the logical flow of ideas. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of practice and training to improve students' ability to construct well-structured essays (Gebremariam, 2023).

Intervention

To address the identified writing challenges in the writing output of grade 12 students, which are cohesion, writing mechanics, and organization and structure, the intervention program entitled "Mechanics Drills and Idea Sequencing for Effective Writing" is proposed. This program is designed to provide explicit instruction in punctuation rules, with an emphasis on correct comma usage; offer guided practice through drills that reinforce mechanical accuracy; teach students how to construct cohesive paragraphs, including the development of clear topic sentences and logically ordered supporting details; and incorporate formative assessment and feedback to monitor progress and adjust instruction accordingly. It aims to address the core weaknesses identified in the study.

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, it can be concluded that Grade 12 students demonstrated moderate ability in responding to writing prompts, particularly in coherence and clarity of ideas, with their outputs showing creativity and a logical progression of thoughts despite minor lapses. However, the students encountered greater difficulties with cohesion, as transitional devices were often used ineffectively, leading to redundancy and run-on sentences. More serious concerns were identified in writing mechanics, organization, and sentence structure, with many outputs containing grammatical errors and structural weaknesses that hindered clear communication of ideas. These results indicate that while students possess the capacity to generate relevant and meaningful ideas, their overall writing performance is significantly affected by weaknesses in cohesion, grammar, and structural organization. Therefore, improving these areas is essential in enhancing the quality of students' written outputs.

Recommendations

In light of the conclusions drawn, several recommendations are proposed. Students should engage in regular, purposeful writing practice, such as journaling, essay drafting, and reflective writing, to strengthen their overall writing proficiency. Teachers are encouraged to integrate viewing-based prompts, such as images, videos, and infographics, into writing instruction to stimulate students' critical thinking and creativity while simultaneously assessing their viewing and writing skills. In addition, teachers should implement short but consistent grammar enhancement activities, such as daily or weekly drills, peer editing sessions, sentence correction tasks, and focused exercises on common weaknesses like subject-verb agreement, punctuation, and sentence construction. Schools may adopt intervention programs such as the Mechanics Drills and Idea Sequencing for Effective Writing Program to systematically address students' needs in grammar and organization. Finally, future researchers are encouraged to conduct experimental studies using control groups and pre-test/post-test designs to determine the effectiveness of such interventions and to explore the impact of various viewing-based prompts on specific dimensions of writing performance.

Author Contributions

Both authors contributed equally to the completion of the study. One author primarily oversaw supervision, validation, and manuscript review, while the other led data collection, analysis, and manuscript preparation.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no competing interests.

AI Use Declaration

This study utilized Grammarly to review and correct grammatical errors in the manuscript.

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